

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME I ISSUE VIII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

DECEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
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Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

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Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17993941

The Endless Pursuit of Wisdom: Understanding the Philosophy of Education

The philosophy of education is the search for wisdom. Education is a process of change in man's individual life. Education is continuous. It is an advance in degrees of enlightenment toward the refinement, improvements, or development of the individual. The natural tendency of man is to acquire education. It is necessary in order to supply potential desires and needs in man. It is necessary for the continuity and fruitful life of things. With man, there is an insatiable desire to know the things around him. The desire is not only in one direction but there is a desire for something constantly and that is the place in which education fits into each effort of man to educate himself into a universal being.

The education shall enable all people to have the opportunities offered by the world. Education shall make the world available to individuals in its different aspects of physical, mental, social and spiritual, transformation. Education is all embraced. Education shall pave way for intellectual and spiritual goals in life. Education is a process of development; it is a lifelong development. The education shall be for all by precept and example. Education may be had in a direct, an indirect or informal way. Education shall ever be in process. Education shall touch the man on each of his sides; the physical side, the mental, the emotional, the social side, etc.

Education is not education for some, but it is a thing that ought to be had by everyone, old and young, in directly or indirectly obtaining; and that it should pertain to the totality of an individual, in making him not only physically fit and intellectually, but morally as well. Education is life. Education grows. It is that which is needed to give directions in life. It is everywhere; there is no stopping of it. And that which makes education a part of the existence of man is that education is a life journey and also life.